

ECONOMIC DISRUPTION, UNIFIED EXCHANGE RATE AND CURRENT ACCOUNT BALANCE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The focus of this study was on the effects of unified exchange rate on trade balance in Nigeria in terms of its negative and positive shocks on the economy. The authors used quarterly data on inflation rate, exchange rate and current account balance pooled from various sources such as Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Global finance data, Central Bank Annual Reports and Accounts. To estimate the model, the author employed Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The result of the study indicated that Lag in current account deficit in the first, second and fourth period (CAD (1,-2,-4)), had significant negative effect on the level of current account deficit; while lag in current account deficit in the third period (CAD (-3)) had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit in Nigeria. Inflation rate in the first period had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit. Exchange rate in the third and fourth period (exr(-3,-4)) had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit. Exchange rate had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit in Nigeria. Inflation had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficits in Nigeria in the reviewed period. Unified exchange rate in the in the reviewed period was unable improve trade competitiveness but rather raised the costs of business operation through increased costs of imports resulting cost push inflation. More importantly, current account deficits in the previous periods had serious adverse impact on current level of trade balance. Implications of the findings: It implies that expenditure switching policy was not effective on Nigeria's economy, probably due to the country's inability to meet the Marshall-Lerner conditions for expenditure switching policy.*

Keywords: *Economic Disruption, Unified Exchange Rate and Current Account Balance*

1.1introduction

Nigeria has witnessed fluctuating exchange rates that have introduced uncertainty in investment, trade balance and flow in foreign trade. It has also resulted in inflationary pressure through rise in

prices suspected to have neutralized the advantage of depreciation. For instance depreciation is meant to stimulate exports and national income; but at the same time, induces a rise in imports that would neutralize part of the positive effect of depreciation thereby resulting in the deterioration in the Nigeria's terms of trade. In Nigeria over the years, depreciation of domestic currency has always resulted in increases in imports prices more than exports prices. A brief history of Nigeria's exchange regimes shows that On the 29th of may Nigeria announced harmonization of dual exchange rate on the basis that it would allow business firms in Nigeria to forecast costs; that it help to determine pricing strategies and maintain stable exchange rate; but exchange rate has continued to soar high. The high cost of exchange rate and falling value of naira may cause diesel and other petroleum product prices to rise, traumatizing the Nigerian economy-the case of economic disruption. Convergence of dual exchange may create artificial scarcity of foreign exchange and bureaucratic bottleneck to cause rise in price. Though it may reverse a deficit balance of payment, it may introduce rising domestic prices and unabated growing consumer prices of goods (Onwuka, 2022). For instance, in 1992, the sharp depreciation in Nigeria, introduced inflationary pressure, rise in interest rate, decline in investment and negative growth (Aliyu, 2021). According to Bekart(1995),falling value of domestic currency may worsen inflationary pressure, create uncertainties in the economy and cause capital outflow.

Nigeria since the late 1970s has continued in what appears to be trial and error in foreign exchange management depending wholly on the neoclassical agents for the management of foreign exchange often landing the country and the entire citizenry on economic crisis and penury. For instance, for fifty three years after the stable period of fixed exchange regime of the period 1960-1970, the country has changed from one to the other without achieving a stable exchange rate. Nigeria witnessed pegged and adjustable regime in the period 1974-1978.The period 1978-1985 saw managed float regime.1986-1990, was a period of acute deregulation of foreign exchange in Nigeria. In 1994, Nigeria practiced dual exchange rate. A brief history of the value and stability of Nigeria's currency shows that Nigeria's currency commanded high value in two periods. First in the period of fixed exchange rate 1960-1970,when Nigeria's pound was at par with the British pound sterling. At this time, Nigeria's pound was one pound to 2.48828 grammas of fine gold. Then the United States dollar had a fixed gold value under the then existing Breton wood system which had a fixed value with the Nigerian pound. In 1967, Britain devalued its currency, due to economic crisis. As Nigeria's currency was pound, it was expected that Nigeria would devalue its currency. For obvious reasons Nigeria did not devalue her currency. First at this time Nigeria's external reserves witnessed a remarkable increase. Second, Nigeria had the fear that devaluation would result in inflationary pressure (Ibe, 2022; CBN, 2020; Dike 2017).

In January 1973, naira replaced pound as Nigeria's currency. At this time naira dollar exchange rate was N1 to \$1.52. Then by February 1973, US dollar was devalued by 10% and naira continued to be

stronger than dollar. By 1974 Central Bank of Nigeria adopted export position strategy to determine exchange rate against dollar (Amuzaga, 2021). At this time naira dollar exchange rate was N1 to \$1.55. By 1984, naira dollar exchange rate was N1 to \$1.2931. Then by December 1984 Nigeria devalued its currency. By 1985, naira dollar exchange rate was N1 to \$1.0004. By July 9th 1986, Nigeria subjected its currency to accelerated depreciation, and then naira exchange rate was N1.2390 to \$1, marking the beginning of the falling value of naira against dollar. Between 1984 and 1986 Nigeria devalued its currency by 19.29%. In 1994 Nigeria adopted regulated and dual exchange rate. Then N22 exchanged for \$1. In 1995 Nigeria modified its exchange rate policy by introducing Autonomous Exchange rate policy, whereby the CBN intervened occasionally by selling foreign currency (Kalu 2021). At this time, parallel market exchange rate was N86 to \$1; while the official rate remained N22 to \$1 (Ekpeyon, 2022).

In Nigeria, excessive spending by various governments-states, local government and federal, puts excess money in the hand of private individuals and businesses, resulting in high demands for imports and the need for foreign exchange which gives rise to much outflow of resources. The rising inflation from domestic currency depreciation gives rise to declining investments and national income. Nigeria's foreign exchange position in terms of value of domestic currency and BOP that has remained in deficits over the years. Various factors have continued to influence exchange rate in Nigeria to the detriment of the national economy. For instance, Nigeria's overdependence on imports for consumption and production increases the demand for foreign exchange resulting in the fall in the value of domestic currency. Even though this scenario may be appropriate for correcting balance of payment problem, the uncontrollable imports in Nigeria cancels out the effect on BOP (Marshall-Lerner condition).

Controlling exchange rate in Nigeria is difficult due to various factors such as difficulty in stabilizing speculation and controlling inflation, corruption in exchange controls. For instance, exchange controls imply direct government intervention in the foreign exchange market through use of import licenses, and exercise controls on capital transactions and at the same time requiring residents of the country to surrender exchange control and obtain approval for foreign exchange. This exercise in Nigeria has led to corruption and fraud on the part of those officials issuing licenses. Exchange control in the Nigerian context, results in policy somersaults in terms of unifying exchange rate (Anyanwu, 2015; Chukwuemeka, 2018). Nigeria spends over N1.3 Trillion per year in food import alone; while import of productive industrial inputs claim several trillion Naira as the country depends wholly on imports for productive inputs (Adesina, 2017). Significant portion of the total imports in Nigeria is explained by much dependence on imports for industrial inputs as well as insignificant local content in the country's industrial sectors. Much importation drains Nigeria's foreign exchange. And improved local and fabrication of spare parts in the industrial sectors are anchored on improved skill and education. Hence, education is meant to solve the problem of requisite skill and the problem of

local content in the Nigerian industrial sector (Ibe, 2016). Therefore, education would serve as the second proxy for development. Devaluation of domestic currency by over 800%, beginning from the 1980s, worsened the country's debt profile, resulting in increasing cost of borrowing, introducing much difficulty in debt repayment (Ogbu, 2002). What is the effect of exchange rate movement on current account balance in Nigeria? What is the effect of inflation rate current account balance in Nigeria? Research Hypotheses: Exchange rate has no significant effect on current account balance in Nigeria. Inflation rate has no significant effect on Current account balance in Nigeria. The general objective of this study is to examine the determinants of external sector sustainability; while the specific objectives are as follows: To examine the effect of exchange rate on current account balance in Nigeria.

Large and persistent current account deficits constitute a cause for concern particularly when sustainability issues are raised. Current account deficits imply unsustainable foreign sector, which has to do with the quality of fiscal management and overall savings of the country. For instance, current account is the difference between national saving and investment which emphasizes the important role of the factors that influence consumption, savings and investment decisions. The main focus of this study is the effect of exchange rate and inflation on current account balance. This study would capture the level of policy somersaults in the use of exchange rate devaluation to correct BOP problems in Nigeria. The outcome of this study has much to do with building the sustainability of the Nigerian foreign sector which determines the level of growth, the level foreign borrowing and the overall welfare of the country.

The outcome of this study would serve as a reference document for government policy adjustment for expenditure policy, economic growth agenda and overall policy readjustment. The results of this study would also be useful to government towards foreign sector sustainability adjustment in Nigeria. Future researchers may find this document necessary for further studies on BOP in Nigeria as the study would contribute to literature. Balance of payment account is used to inform governmental authorities of the international position of the country. It is often used to aid governmental authorities in reaching decisions on monetary and fiscal policies as well as decisions on trade and payment questions. Balance and payments accounts are used to measure the resource flows between one country and another. The information on the payments accounts and receipts in foreign exchange constitute a foreign exchange budget that helps to assure monetary authorities that country go on buying foreign goods and meeting payments in currency when due. They are used to measure the influence of foreign transactions on the national income.

The geographical scope is Nigeria; while the area study Nigeria's foreign sector. The period of study was 2000-2022. The data for the study are annual data on current account balance, inflation rate and exchange rate. The time series data were pooled from World Bank Development Indicators, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics and various sources. All types of

academic research always are confronted with similar challenges such as lack of funds, imprecise data, time constraints, limited literature etc. Due to competing human needs and wants, one may not have sufficient financial resources to carry out extensive and meticulous research. Hence, this study witnessed the same problems. However, the researcher was able to overcome these problems.

2.0 Review of Relevant Literature

2.1. Conceptual Issues

Current account balance is the of all transactions other than those in financial items involving exchange of economic values which takes place between residents and nonresident entities. Current account is the records of all flows of goods, services and transfers, broadly divided into two parts, Balance of Trade (BOT), which deals with only exports and imports of merchandise or visible items, and Balance of Invisible trade (BOI) that records net receipts of invisible items such as dividends, interests, royalties, travels, insurance, banking, transportations and unilateral transfers. Each of these transactions involves foreign currencies, associated with rate of exchange of currency. Foreign exchange rate expresses the value of one currency for another or price of one currency for another determined by demand for and supply of foreign exchange. When the supply is equal to demand the rate of exchange is said to be at par. If the supply of foreign exchange is greater than demand, the value of foreign currency falls below the par and the price of domestic currency rises above it. Several factors determine the demand for and the supply of foreign exchange. Foreign exchange rate expresses the value of one currency in terms of another. It is the price of one unit of foreign currency for the domestic currency (Salvatore, 2021). Exchange rate is the value of domestic currency compared to the value of foreign currencies which is determined by the demand for and the supply of foreign currency. Exchange rate is established at the point where the demand for and the supply of foreign exchange meet. Countries suffer that acute structural inadequacies such as over dependence on imports of industrial raw materials and requisite skills for industrial production suffer much demand for foreign exchange. On the supply side of foreign exchange, most sources of foreign exchange in the developing countries are unpredictable and dependent on exogenous factors.

Debit items in the current account balance such as imports of all sorts, services rendered by foreigners, trade expenditures, interest and dividends on securities, remittances to charitable organizations, government expenditures outside the country, export of long term capital, or imports of foreign stocks and bonds, direct investment, loans to foreigners and imports of gold influence the demand for foreign exchange. On the other hand, credit items of the current account balance such as commodity exports, services rendered to foreigners, travel expenditures by foreigners in Nigeria, interest dividends on foreign securities owned by Nigerians, remittances and charitable contributions by foreigners to Nigeria, government expenditures in Nigeria by foreign nations, imports of long term capital, i.e. exports of stocks and bonds to Nigeria by foreigners, FDI in Nigeria, foreign loans to Nigeria, imports of short term capital ie increase of foreign owned bank balances in Nigeria, gold

exports and miscellaneous export items. A country with surplus on the current account balance is said to have strong exchange rate position; while country with deficit on her current account balance is said to have weak exchange rate position. Short term and long term capital influence exchange rate movement; while exchange rate movements induce inflation. The inflow and outflow of hot money from capital movement will cause change in exchange rate. Inflow of capital raises exchange rate value; while outflow lowers exchange rate value. Studies have shown that interest rate differentials between two countries provide evidence that there is a high and increasing degree of internal capital mobility According to Montiel(2022),there is a strong correlation between the shares of aggregate savings in GDP and shares of savings in investment and capital flow in a country. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) as a form of capital flow or portfolio investment in equities may be attracted by the opportunities to use local raw material or abundance of local labor force (Taylor&Sarno, 2021).

Capital movements both short term and long term influence exchange rate movements. In Keynes's view, technological improvements result in productivity, cheaper goods and services, changes tariff, exports subsidies, and changes in exchange rates, through reciprocal demand, independent of international price movements. Also, capital movements both short term and long term influence exchange rate movements. The inflow and outflow of capital give rise to changes in exchange rates. The inflow tends to raise the foreign exchange value of the country receiving the capital; while the outflow tends to lower it. Other factors that influence exchange rates are tariffs, speculations etc. In actual sense, expected change in domestic currency price for foreign currency, leads to inflow and outflow of hot money to cause further change in exchange rate. The inflow tends to raise the foreign exchange value of the country receiving the capital; while the outflow tends to lower it. Other factors that influence exchange rates are tariffs, speculations etc. In actual sense, expected change in domestic currency price for foreign currency, leads to inflow and outflow of hot money to cause further change in exchange rate. No factor can influence the exchange rate except it first influences the demand for and supply of foreign exchange. Purchasing power theory ignores this influence. Inflow of capital may provide both motive and the resources for capital out flow especially in a situation where borrowed funds are transferred abroad .Government can borrow money and sell to domestic residents who may transfer the money abroad through legal or illegal means. In this case government is the provider of foreign exchange. This is a case of debt fuelled capital outflow. In response to political and financial crisis, heavier taxes, prospective tightening of capital control or major devaluation, hot money may leave a country to another country .This is a case of debt driven outflow. Capital outflow can be influenced by exchange rate misalignment, financial sector constraint, fiscal deficits and external incentives, corruption of political leaders and extra ordinary access to government funds.

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Due to external borrowing residents of a country are motivated to move their assets to foreign country, this is a case of debt driven capital outflow. To capture both debt driven and debt fuelled outflow in this study, the secondary market prices of Nigeria's sovereign debt which reflects the opportunities and risks in investing in Nigeria as a proxy. Due to innovative ideas or policy changes of government or natural events or technological revolution, there appears to be economic disruption or shock or structural breaks within the economy, which changes the status quo. Hence, economic disruption may either be exogenous or endogenous. And if endogenous due attention is paid to forecasting the future occurrence or needs and how to meet emergent scenario. The focus of the present study is the effects of policy changes on foreign exchange rate management from dual exchange rate policy to single exchange rate on capital flows (inflow and outflows) in Nigeria. International capital flow is the flow of bond and equity across countries. Private bond and equity have become crucial source of financing large current account imbalances. Portfolio investment and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflow indicate growing external financing. Capital flees or leaves a country in response to attendant economic circumstances. Under heavy debt burden there is possibility of crowding out of domestic capital. With serious economic crisis in which cost of is high there is divestment for the avoidance of heavy taxes and expropriation risk and fiscal crisis. In this kind of situation a nation can suffer capital flight or capital outflow. Capital out flow can disrupt the economy in various ways. It reduces the rate of capital formation in a country. It can adversely affect the current and future prospects of a country as well as causing short term liquidity shortage in an economy, resulting in rising interest, declining investment and poor economic growth. It reduces government revenue and weakens capacity to service debt. It worsens balance of payment crisis and capable of compounding foreign finance problems of a heavily indebted country (Ajayi, 2021).

Capital movement both in the short term and in the long term influence exchange rate movement ;while the expected change in the domestic price of foreign currency influences inflow and outflow of hot money resulting in further change in exchange rate value. Inflow of capital raises exchange rate; while outflow lowers exchange rate value (Dewett & Navalur, 2013). A fluctuating exchange rate movement discourages long term international investment inflow, dislocates internal economy, and encourages huge capital out flow. There is a mixed blessing behind currency devaluation. When savings and investment are unbalanced across countries, capital inflow becomes necessary. International capital markets react to shock in one country through a change in capital flow change in prices of country's financial claim. The determinants of capital flows are the level of openness of the economy, investment opportunities available in the global economy, co variances between expected returns on various investment projects, government policies and capital market imperfections, credit ratings, labor conditions and exchange rate policies of a country as well as black market exchange rate premium. Secondary market prices of sovereign debt explain capital flows as it reflects opportunities and risks of investing in a country. Industrial production is a global factor determinant of capital

flows. Net and gross capital flows respond to economic fundamentals, official policies and financial market imperfections, rules concerning repatriation of capital, rights to repatriation of dividends without restrictions, rate of returns on capital and income (Ahuja, 2016; Todaro & Smith 2012).

The use of depreciation to correct BOP problem under flexible regime leads to vicious circle of inflation. Depreciation itself leads to a rise in imports prices, and cost push inflation. And at the same time exports prices rise. With the rise in cost of living, money wage would rise to intensify inflation. Theoretically, there are conditions under which devaluation leads to improved national income.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 Keynesian Theory of Balance of Payment Deficits-the Twin Deficits

The Keynesian models assume that a higher fiscal deficits resulting from lower taxes or higher government spending increases disposable income, consumption and decreases private savings which give impetus to higher current account balance. The economic reaction of private agents under the Keynesian model supports the twin deficits hypothesis that wider fiscal deficits are accompanied by wider current account deficits. And if the fiscal situation is perceived by agents as increasingly unsustainable, then tax increases. The relationship between exchange rate and current account balance is associated with the evolution of the monetary system and trade policy. The use of depreciation to correct BOP problem under flexible regime leads to vicious circle of inflation. Depreciation itself leads to a rise in imports prices, and cost push inflation. And at the same time exports prices rise. With the rise in cost of living, money wage would rise to intensify inflation. Theoretically, there are conditions under which devaluation leads to improved national income.

2.2.2 Marshall –Lerner Theory of Trade Balance

Marshall-Lerner conditions by the British economist Alfred Marshall (1842-1924) and Romanian economist Abba P. Lerner (1905-1985), concerning trade stated that the existence of currency devaluation could lead to improved national income. The question is how devaluation works to improve balance of payments. As a result of reduction in the value of domestic currency, with respect to foreign currency, prices of exports fall. And prices of imports go up. This encourages exports and discourages imports. With exports so stimulated and imports discouraged deficits in the balance of payment tend to decrease. This process is referred to as expenditure switching policy. The whole essence of this policy is to increase exports earnings through lowering of exports prices as a way of stimulating demand. Then Marshall and Lerner developed a condition which states that devaluation will succeed in improving the balance of payment if the sum of the price elasticity of exports and price elasticity of imports is greater than one. Hence, devaluation improves balance of payment if

$$e_x + e_m > 1$$

Where if e_x stands for price elasticity of export; e_m stands for price elasticity of imports. If this is on the contrary, devaluation of domestic currency adversely affects balance of payments position instead

of improving it. On the other hand if the sum of e_x and e_m is equal to unity (1) there will be balance of payment equilibrium.

Fernandez-Arias & Montiel (1996) Theory of Capital Flow.

The focus of this theory is the effects of domestic and global factors on capital flows. For instance, assuming capital flows are transactions in different types of assets n and indexed as:

$$S = F(1, \dots, n) \dots \dots (1), .$$

The domestic returns on assets of types may be decomposed into two components—a project level of expected return (G_s), and an adjustment factor dependent on credit wordiness of country of interest

.The project level return is assumed to be a function of a vector of net flows(F) that ,

$$(C_s) f(S_{-1} + F) \dots (2), \text{ where } S_{-1} \dots \dots \dots = \text{initial}$$

stocks of liabilities. Given that external creditors would diversify their portfolios, the opportunity cost of assets of type S, V is a function of S . In this, Fernandez-Arias and Montiel (1996) established an arbitrage condition for which F can be resolved. Vector of net flows- f can be solved by shift factors (g, c and v for domestic environment domestic credit wordiness (pull factors) and financial conditions of creditor country (push factors). The shift factors- g, c, v have their increasing factors as G_s, C_s, V_s respectively. This is functionally presented as: $G_s(g, F) * C_s(S_{-1} + F) = V_s(V, S_{-1} + F)$. The desired value of the net flows- F, F^* is implicitly determined by the equation 1 above and can be alternatively presented as: $F^*(g, c, v, S_{-1}) \dots \dots \dots (2)$

F^* Increases in g, c but decreases in v and S_{-1} . By holding S_{-1} constant and differentiating eq 2 we have: $\Delta F^* = F_1^* \Delta g + F_2^* \Delta C + F_3^* \Delta v \dots \dots \dots (3)$

Subscripts denote partial derivatives. Equation 3 above describes the pattern of changes in expected capital flows due to changes in the pull factors (g, c) and push factors (v, S_{-1}) and by the initial values of S . Increases in g and c and decreases in v may induce prolonged growth in capital flows. And differences in the short term and long term capital movements are due to the magnitude of changes in g, c and v . Permanent changes in g, c and v may cause long run and permanent changes in the pattern of net flows, whereas transitory changes in these factors result in transitory short term changes in net capital flows which may be reversed over time. International capital markets react to shocks in one country through changes in prices of countries financial claim. There are two sets of explanatory variables: the country specific factors (credit rating and black market exchange rate premiums), and global market factor such as industrial production.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Adejuri (2025) Examined the effect of exchange rate unification on economic performance in Nigeria. The author employed quarterly data on exchange rate, imports and exports as well as inflation rate

from 2023 to 2025. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method was employed to estimate the model. The results of the analysis indicated that that exchange rate has significant effect on imports. Exchange rate had significant negative effect on exports in Nigeria.

Akinduro(2025) examined the effect of exchange rate unification on Nigerian economy. The following variables were examined: exchange rate, imports, and domestic investment. The study made use of quarterly data from 2023-2025. To estimate the model the study used Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The result of the analysis indicated that exchange rate movement had significant negative effect on imports and domestic investment in Nigeria.

Andohol (2020) assessed whether the J-Curve model is affected by structural breaks in Nigeria from 1970 to 2018, and using the 1986 SAP as a criterion to identify break periods as Pre- and Post-SAP. The study employed both linear and nonlinear ARDL models and concluded that the J-Curve hypothesis is not supported for Nigeria. However, the study found an N-shaped pattern during the overall and post-SAP periods, indicating the potential relevance of structural breaks in shaping the J-Curve's typology.

Ayinde & Fakile(2025) examined the effect of exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. The following variables were examined: exchange rate, foreign direct investment, and inflation rate. The authors made use of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method for analysis. The results of the analysis indicated that exchange rate movement had significant negative effect on both foreign direct investment and domestic investment.

Baba and Yazici (2016) also looked at the bilateral J-curve and the Marshall-Lerner (ML) condition between Nigeria and European Union countries between 1999Q1 and 2012Q4. Using the ARDL approach, the study showed no evidence of the J-curve or satisfaction of the Marshall-Lerner condition between Nigeria and the EU15 countries. The study, however, found evidence supporting the J-curve hypothesis in the short run between Nigeria and Austria, Denmark, Germany, and Italy and the existence of the Marshall-Lerner condition only in Luxembourg.

Brown & Green (2026) examined the effect of exchange rate unification on economic growth in Nigeria in the period 2023-2026 using quarterly data. These authors captured exchange rate, domestic investment and foreign direct investment. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) was employed to estimate the model. The results of the analysis indicated that unified exchange rate had significant negative effect on Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria.

Edwards and Garlick (2018) studied South Africa. The study found that the movement of the real exchange rate had a sensitive influence on trade volume. Whereas depreciation of the nominal exchange rate in the long run only has a limited impact on the trade balance due to the influence of domestic inflation. A similar finding was also shown by Edwards & Lawrence (2016) for the trade balance case for 44 manufacturing industries in the period 1990-2002. Using the Panel Data Method, it is found that depreciation in the real exchange rate can increase the trade balance for non-

commodity manufactured products. The panel estimation results show that one percent depreciation is expected to increase the value of exports relative to imports by around 0.7 percent.

Jackson et al. (2021) examined the J-curve phenomenon in Sierra Leone from 2002Q2 to 2019Q4 using the unrestricted vector autoregressive (VAR) technique. The study showed a long-run positive relationship between the exchange rate and trade balance and that the Marshall-Lerner (ML) condition was also satisfied. Other studies also found evidence of the J-curve in different countries.

Johnson (2024) examined the implications of exchange rate unification for Nigeria's economic stability. The author examined the relationship between inflation and exchange rate movement using quarterly data. The researcher made use of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method for analysis. The study discovered that unification of exchange rate had significant negative effect on inflation rate in Nigeria especially in the short run.

Jones & Brown (2025) examined the effect of dual exchange rate system on the Nigerian economy. The authors captured the demand for and the supply for dollars, exchange rate, inflation and foreign direct investment in Nigeria in the period 1980-2025. For analysis, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique was used for analysis. The result of the analysis indicated that exchange rate had significant positive effect on inflation; while it had significant negative effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

Ogbonna (2018) utilized the co integration technique to examine the presence of the Marshall-Lerner condition and J-Curve phenomenon in Nigeria's foreign trade activities. The study did not verify the Marshall-Lerner condition for Nigeria or the J-curve effect.

Olawomi & Mohammed (2025) examined the effect of exchange rate unification on macroeconomic performance in Nigeria using quarterly data for the period 2023-2025. The authors captured the following variables: exchange rate, inflation and foreign direct investment. To estimate the variables, the authors made use of OLS. The results of the analysis indicated that exchange rate had significant positive effect on inflation in Nigeria. Exchange rate had significant negative effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

Setyo & Sielvia (2023), studied the relationship between exchange rate and trade balance in Indonesia from 1986 to 2018 (33 years) using the Vector Auto regression (VAR) Model. The study examined the possibility of the J-Curve effect in Indonesia's trade balance. The main findings of this study are: in Indonesia, from 1986 to 2018, the value of net trade last year brings a small effect on the value of the exchange rate. However, it significantly reacts to the shock on the exchange rate, although it is not depicted as the J-Curve effect. Husman (2017) studied similar topics for Indonesia in the period 1993-2004. The study came with findings that the overall sample showed that Marshall-Lerner conditions were satisfied. This resulted in dissatisfaction with the case of Singapore and the UK because export demand was not elastic.

Siregar and Hasanah (2023) examined the effect of the real exchange rate on Indonesia's bilateral trade balance for the period 1996-2011. The study was conducted on three major Indonesian trading partners, namely the US, China, and Japan, using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The results concluded that the trade balance between Indonesia-China and Indonesia-Japan showed the occurrence of the Marshall-Lerner Condition and the J-Curve Curve Phenomenon, while in the US Indonesia bilateral trade; it had not yet been seen. Thorbecke (2015) studied Indonesia, Malaysia and Thailand. The study indicated that changes in exchange rates can affect trade. This study showed a decline in exports as a result of exchange rate depreciation in Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand. Williams (2024) examined transparency and credibility issues in Nigeria's dual exchange rate system. The author made use of qualitative research design. The outcome of the study indicated that corruption and lack of transparency resulted in the scarcity of foreign exchange, high cost of business and inflation in Nigeria.

3.0 Methodology

Marshall and Lerner developed a condition which states that devaluation will succeed in improving the balance of payment if sum of price elasticity of exports and price elasticity of imports is greater than one. Hence, devaluation improves balance of payment if $e_x + e_m > 1$

Where if e_x stands for price elasticity of export; e_m stands for price elasticity of imports. If this is on the contrary, devaluation adversely affects balance of payments position instead of improving it. On the other hand if the sum of e_x and e_m is equal to unity (1) there will be balance of payment equilibrium. Nigeria's inability to meet Marshall- Lerner condition may result in policy somersaults. The effects of unified exchange rate on trade balance has two phase impacts – short term disruption due to currency depreciation and long term improvement in trade competitiveness aligning with the J-curve phenomenon and depending seriously on Marshall- Lerner condition, otherwise the whole exercise would end up in increased costs of living ,high inflation and capital outflow.

Model Specification

Recognizing the channels of interactions, between current account balance, exchange rate and inflation rate in Nigeria, the empirical model for this study is specified as: $CAB = f(exr, infl)$ -----(2.1)

CAB is current account balance; exr is exchange rate; infl is inflation rate. Equation 2.1 is rewritten as: $CAB = \alpha_0 + exr \alpha_1 + infl \alpha_2 + \varepsilon_1$ Where α_0 is intercept; α_1 is the coefficient of exchange rate; α_2 is the coefficient of inflation; ε_1 is the error term.

3.3 Model Estimation Method

To estimate equation 2.1, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method would be employed after subjecting the time series data to unit root or stationarity test to determine the time properties of the data. Unit root test is pre-test usually used to identify if a time series data are stationary or not, in order to prevent a spurious regression. Such test ensures the validity of the following test statistics: t-test

statistic and coefficients of determination of R^2 . There are diverse techniques for unit root tests such as, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Phillips-Perron test statistic, Kwiatkowski-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) test statistic and N.g Perron (NP). There are often debates among researchers over choice of technique for the unit root test. Gujarati, Porter & Gunasekar (2012) remarked that there is no empirical proof over the superiority of any technique over another; instead, these techniques complement each other. Ipso facto, this study therefore employs Phillips-Perron unit root test statistic using ADF for confirmation.

$$\Psi_t = \rho \psi_{t-1} + U_t \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

In which $-1 \leq \rho \leq 1$, where ψ is an element representing all the variables in the study and U_t is the white noise. If $\rho = 1$ then equation above is a random walk model without drift (non-stationary stochastic process). This means that ψ is non-stationary at time t . This is the general idea behind test of stationarity. If $\rho = 1$, the above equation cannot be estimated by OLS as the test will be severely biased by a case of unit root. Hence, this equation is manipulated as follows: subtract ψ_{t-1} on both sides of the equation we obtain:

$$\Psi_t - \psi_{t-1} = \rho \psi_{t-1} - \psi_{t-1} - U_t \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

This can be alternatively rewritten as:

$$\Delta \Psi_t - \delta \psi_{t-1} + U_t \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

Where $\delta = (\rho - 1)$ and Δ as usual is the first difference operator.

In practice, therefore instead of estimating equation 3.20, we estimate equation 3.21 and test the null hypothesis that $\delta = 0$ and the alternative hypothesis being that $\delta < 0$. Note: if $\delta = 0$, then $\rho = 1$, meaning that time series under consideration is non stationary. If $\delta = 0$, the equation will become: $\Delta \Psi_t = \psi_{t-1} - \psi_{t-1} = U_t \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$

Since U_t is the white noise error term, it is stationary, meaning that the first differences of a random walk time series are stationary. Now, equation (3.4) can be estimated by taking the first differential of Ψ_t and regress them on ψ_{t-1} and see if the estimated slope coefficient ($=\delta$) in this regression is zero or not. If it is zero, we conclude that $\Delta \Psi_t$ is non-stationary. Nevertheless, if it is negative we conclude that Ψ_t is stationary. The pretest procedure for the unit root test adopted in this study is Philips-Perron (PP) unit root test.

3.4 Philips- Perron (PP) Unit Root Test

Philip and Perron test takes care of the possible serial correlation in the error terms without adding the lagged difference terms of the regress and. PP test also, does error correction. Phillips and Perron mechanism is represented as:

$$RC = \beta_1 + \beta_2 t + \delta \gamma_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \gamma_{t-i} + \dots\dots\dots (3.5),$$

Where ε_t is a pure white noise error term?

RC_{t-1} = dependent variable in the first period; while RC_{t-2} is that of the second period etc.

3.4.3 Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing co-integration.

Unlike single co-integration tests which are applicable if time series are serially integrated that is purely $1(0)$ and $1(I)$, ARDL bounds testing co-integration is applicable if the variables are fractionally integrated at $1(0)$ and $1(I)$. Long run and short-run unrestricted ARDL bounds testing approach as was developed in 2001 by Pesaran, shin and Smith (Pesaran, shin & Smith, 2001) is specified below as: $\Delta \ln capfl = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta \ln EXR_{-i} + \lambda ecm_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (3.6)$

Decision rule:

Reject H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls above the upper critical bounds at chosen level of significance and accept H_0 if otherwise. Do not Reject H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls below the lower critical bounds at chosen level of significance. Take no decision about H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls inside the lower and upper critical bounds at chosen level of significance. The short run relationship among the variables is specified as:

$$\Delta \ln psect = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln eexr + \alpha_1 t_{-1} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots 3.7$$

Where μ_t is the white noise or error term and the first part of the write hand side of equation 3.28 with parameter β_1 to β_6 represents the long-run parameters of the model and the second part with parameters α_2 to α_6 represent the short-run parameters of the model.

ARDL bounds testing hypotheses is stated as:

H_0 : the variables are not co-integrated

H_1 : the variables are co-integrated

Where ecm_{t-1} is the short-run dynamic error correction factor, λ is the coefficient of ecm_{t-1} that measures the speed of adjustment in the short-run into the long run and μ_t is the white noise error term. If the coefficient of ecm_{t-1} is negative we then conclude that there exists short-run relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable. As a result, the study analysis will rely on short run results because of the advantages short-run results have over long-run results.

3.5 Evaluation of Estimates

The evaluation of estimates is divided into three stages

Economic a-priori criteria

Statistical Criteria: first order test

Econometric Criteria: second order Test

Economic criteria (a-priori expectation): Economic criteria refer to the expected signs and magnitude of the estimated parameters concerning economic relationships between the independent variables and dependent variable as propounded by theories. It is one of the criteria used in determining whether the estimates are theoretically meaningful (Gujarati, Porter & Gunasekar, 2012).

Based on economic theories therefore, the independent variables are expected to take the following signs in relation to the dependent variable in this study.

Statistical Criteria (First Order Test): This stage includes: the coefficient of determination (R^2), adjusted coefficient of determination (R^{-2}), t-statistics and F-statistic.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2): Coefficient of determination is used to measure the explanatory power of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables. It denotes the percentage of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable. Therefore, the higher and closer the R^2 is to unity, the higher is the explanatory power of the explanatory variables and vice versa. If on the other hand, $R = 0$, it indicates that the explanatory variables could not explain the changes in the dependent variable, R^2 ranges from 0 to + 1. **The Adjusted Coefficient of**

Determination (R^{-2}): Coefficient of determination (R^2) does not take into account the loss of degrees of freedom from the introduction of additional explanatory variables in the function which in fact raises the value of R^2 . To correct this defect, adjusted coefficient of determination (R^{-2}) is introduced to take into account the penalty of introducing additional explanatory variables. Adjusted coefficient of determination clearly decreases as new regressors which do not add value to the model are introduced.

T-Statistic: This is used to test the individual statistical significance of the estimated parameters. Decision rule for t-Statistic is stated as thus: Reject H_0 if t-computed is greater than t-tabulated and accepts H_0 if otherwise. **F-Statistic:** This test is used in regression analysis for conducting overall significance of the regression. Decision rule for F-Statistic is stated as thus: reject H_0 if the calculated F - statistic (F^*) is greater than the tabulated F-value, and accept H_0 if otherwise stated at chosen level of significance with ($V_1; V_2$) degree of freedom. Where $V_1 = K-1$ and $V_2 = n-k$, n is the number of observations and K is the number of parameters.

3.5.1 Econometric criteria (Second Order Test):

This aims at investigating if the assumptions of the classical linear regression model are met in this study. The following econometric criteria are examined: Normality test. This study employs normality test in order to ascertain if the error term in the regression model is normally distributed or not. The test follows a residual diagnostics checking precisely Jarque-Bera which follows chi-square probability distribution (Gujarati, 2004).

Hypothesis: $H_0: U_i = 0$ (the error term follows a normal distribution)

$H_1: U_i \neq 0$ (the error term does not follow a normal distribution)

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if $\chi^2_{cal} > \chi^2_{tab}$, and accept H_0 if otherwise.

Test for Autocorrelation: This is a problem which is usually associated with any time series data. This paper employs Durbin-Watson (D-W) technique for autocorrelation test. According to Gujarati (2004) Durbin-Watson has optional asymptotic properties and is more efficient for all sample sizes. The D-W value is used to ascertain whether or not there exists the presence of autocorrelation.

Autocorrelation hypothesis: $H_0: u_i = 0$ (the error terms are not auto correlated with a first order scheme)

$H_0: u_i \neq 0$ (the error terms are auto correlated with a first order scheme)

Decision Rule

If $0 < d < d_L$, reject H_0 of no positive autocorrelation

If $4 \leq d \leq d_u$, take no decision on H_0 of no positive autocorrelation.

If $4 - d_L < d < 4$, Reject H_0 of no negative autocorrelation

If $4 - d_u \leq d < (4 - d_L)$, take no decision on H_0

If $d_u < d < 4 - d$, do not reject H_0 of no autocorrelation, positive or negative.

Muticollinearity test: Muti-collinearity test is used to dictate the presence of exact linear relationship among some or all explanatory variables of a regression model. Multi-co linearity is inherent in most economic relationships and can be dictated using the correlation matrix. Once the pair wise correlation coefficient between two or more explanatory variables are in excess of 0.8, we then conclude that there is presence of multi-collinearity between the variables signifying that there is an exact influence among the explanatory variables on the dependent variable.

Test for Heteroskedasticity: An important assumption of the classical linear regression model is that disturbance term “U” appearing in the population regression function is homoskedastic, which means the U’s all have the same variance (Gujarati, 2004). Violation of this assumption leads to standard errors and t-values that are biased. Such bias leads to wrong as well as faulty conclusions regarding the statistical significance of the ECM estimates. This paper employs Breusch-Pagan-Godfray (BPG) test in order to ascertain whether the error term of the regression model are homoskedastic and/or has a constant variance.

Hypothesis: $H_0: U's = 0$ (the error terms are homoskedastic)

$H_1: U's \neq 0$ (the error terms are heteroskedastic)

Decision rule: reject H_0 if the calculated χ^2 is greater than critical value of χ^2 at chose level of significance and accept H_0 if stated otherwise.

Sources of Data

The author made use of quarterly data on inflation rate, current account balance and exchange rate sourced from IMF data, Global Finance data, CBN statistical Bulletin, CBN Annual Reports and Accounts, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The software for data analysis of the above data was E – views 10.

4.1 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Unit Root Test Result

Table 4.1: PP Test Result: Do not reject Ho, if $t^* > PP$ critical value

	1%crit	At Level	p-val		1% crit.	1 st difference	p-val	
CAB	-3.57772	-5.850146	0.0136	1 (1)	-6.6130022	-3.581152	0.0000	1 (1)
Infl	-	-1.757028	0.3967	1 (0)	-3.581152	-8.466135	0.0000	1 (1)
Exr	-3.577723	211.3029	0.9999	1 (0)	-3.677837	-3.6000987	0.00310	1 (0)
Cpi	-3.577723	-5.854072	0.0000	1 (1)	-3.581152	-5.715046	0.0000	1 (1)

Source: Researcher's computation

Table 4.1 above shows that current account balance

Current account balance (CAB) was stationary at levels and stationary after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e. 1(1). Inflation (Infl) was not stationary at levels but stationary after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e.1 (1). Exchange rate (Exr) was not stationary at levels but stationary after the first difference and integrated of order zero i.e.1 (0). Consumer Price Index(CPI) was both stationary at levels and after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e.1(1). Since not all the variables were integrated of order one ARDL technique is more for the final analysis. Phillip Peron test results indicated that current account balance was stationary both at levels and after the first difference and integrated at order one. Inflation rate was stationary at both at levels and after the first difference and integrated at order one. Exchange rate was both stationary at both levels and after the first difference and integrated at order zero.

Table 4.2: ARDL test Result

Dependent Variable: CAB

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	Probability
CAB(-1)	-2.119228	0.308173	-6.876740	0.0005
CAB(-2)	-1.207325	0.259081	-4.660030	0.0035
CAB(-3)	77.41018	24.30999	3.184294	0.0190
CAB(-4)	-34.01243	23.42705	-1451844	0.1967
Infl	18579109	39495577	0.470410	0.6547
Infl(-1)	71257771	35609430	2.001093	0.0530
Infl(-2)	38847072	40810446	0.951890	0.3719
Exr	1717131	6599983	0.260172	0.8034
Exr(-1)	-7209534	11160916	-0.645963	0.5422
Exr(-2)	-28979090	15947428	-1.817164	0.1191
Exr(-3)	59612173	A8374452	3.341967	0.0157

Exr(-4)	60016696	10773175	5.570948	0.0014
C	2.696EX08	9.25EX08	0.290626	0.7811

Source: Researcher's computation

R-Squared	0.966562	Mean dependent var	-1.52E+08
Adj.R-Squared	0.894112	S.D dependent Var	7.91E+08
S.E.of Regression	2.57E+08	Akaike infor Criterion	41.76537
Sum Squared Resid	3.97E +17	Schwartz Criterion	42.46239
Log Likelihood	-403.6537	Hanan-Qinin criterion	41..90144
F-Statistic	13.34113	Durbin-Watson Stat.	2.080000
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002247		

Table 4.2 above shows the ARDL test results of this study. The results indicated that lag in current account balance in the first period (CAB(-1)) had significant negative impact on trade balance at less than 5% level of significance in Nigeria over the period 2000-2023. For every 1% rise in trade balance, lag in current account in the first period had a depressing effect of 2.1%. In the second period, lag in current account balance (CAB (-2)) had significant negative impact at less than 5% level of significance on trade balance. For every 1% increase in trade balance, lag in the second period had a depressing effect of -1.21%. Lag in the current account balance in the third period (CAB (-3)) had significant positive effect at less than 5% level of significance on current account balance. For every 1% rise in trade balance, trade balance in the previous contributed 77.41%. Lag in the fourth period in current balance (CAB (-4)) had significant negative impact on trade balance at less than 5% level of significance. Lag in inflationary pressure in the first period had significant positive effect on trade balance. Lag in the second period had also positive effect but not significant at 5% level of significance. Lag in exchange rate movement in both first and second periods had negative effect but the effect was not significant at 5% level. In the third and fourth periods lags in exchange rate movement had significant negative effects at less than 5% level of significance on trade balance in Nigeria. The model has goodness of fit as the R-Squared of 0.9665 implies that the model can explain 97% of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. And with the Durbin-Watson statistical level of 2.08, the model is free from auto correlation.

5.1 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation.

Summary: Lag in current account deficit in the first, second and fourth period (CAD (1,-,2,-4)), had significant negative effect on the level of current account deficit; while lag in current account deficit in the third period (CAD (-3)) had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit in Nigeria. Inflation rate in the first period had significant positive effect on the level of current account

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deficit. Exchange rate in the third and fourth period ($exr(-3,-4)$) had significant positive effect on the level of current account deficit. The findings implied that unified exchange rate / currency devaluation could not improve on the trade balance as well as trade competitiveness in Nigeria. Through increased imports cost, it worsened costs of business operations, resulting in inflationary pressure in Nigeria.

Implications: Implications: Expenditure switching policy was not effective on Nigerian economy in the reviewed period probably due to the country's inability to meet Marshall-Lerner condition for the effectiveness of devaluation of domestic currency on improving trade balance and achieving trade competitiveness

Conclusion: Unified exchange rate did not accomplish the policy objective of trade competitiveness but worsened the level of inflation through increased costs of business operation in Nigeria.

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